

Empirical Review of Experiences of Women Academicians in Higher Education

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: January 25,2025</p> <p>Accepted: April 26,2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Women, Higher Education,Academicians, Masculine</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15287595</p>	<p>Purpose <i>This article examines the experiences of women academicians in higher education. Historically, women academicians were kept inferior to men, due to masculine hegemony, in exercising the power, enjoying status and privileges.</i></p> <p>Design/Methodology/Approach <i>We skimmed the findings of several research studies on women's academic lived experiences from different research databases. We sorted out journals on gender and higher education from Tylor and Francis, Eric education, Science direct, and Google scholar. We reviewed 150 research articles, using the cited database software till reaching the point of saturation.</i></p> <p>Findings <i>The results revealed that society is male dominant structure and hostile to women. Furthermore, taken-for-granted gender assumptions and beliefs in higher education institutions operate to make women conform to structures of disadvantage and experience repressive gender relations. We reach on the argument that men academicians explicitly manipulate the fate of the women academicians in higher education.</i></p> <p>Research Implications <i>The findings of the current study suggested that women can get senior and powerful positions if they are given a women-friendly environment and equitable chance in higher education. It is suggested to revisit the higher education policies in developing countries to provide equal space for men and women.</i></p> <p>Practical Implication <i>This article has practical implications for all the developing countries to take initiatives in higher education to further improve the women's status in higher education institutions. This research can be utilized by academicians and research scholars to further extend the research and examine the partialities of the existing structure.</i></p> <p>Social Implication <i>This research will be helpful for all the academic institutions in public and private sector to reform the educational institutions. it will be fruitful to improve the status of women in society.</i></p> <p>Originality <i>This research work is synthesized from the different research studies conducted on higher education across the world. As certified data bases are used to skim and analyze the literature.</i></p>

Introduction

For the last few decades, a significant increase of women academicians in higher education is indicative of women's struggle to enter and work along with men (Tran & Nguyen, 2020; Wadia, 2020; Yusufzada, Xia, & Sediqi, 2020). Women academicians experience insufficient space even though they reached the pinnacles of power (Semela, Bekele, & Abraham, 2020; Stahl, McDonald, & Loeser, 2020). Within the context of the increasing demands of women academicians in higher education, it is important to study the experiences of women academicians in higher education vis-a-vis to men (Sahar & Kaunert, 2020; Sankar & Aruna, 2020; Selthun, 2020). It is also pertinent to focus on the women's experiences in the academic environment, in which women's potential for academia is recognized and rewarded (Ren & Caudle, 2020). Thus, it is an attempt to explore the experiences of women academicians in higher education institutions. Before turning to the experiences of women academicians, we start by discussing the wider context.

The experience of women academicians in higher education has been the subject of debate over the past decades in developed countries (M. Rehman & Siddiqui, 2020). A substantial body of research work on women's experiences in higher education in the West has been carried out during the past few decades (Olson-Strom & Rao, 2020; H. Rehman, Moazzam, & Ansari, 2020). These research studies conclude that higher education institutions are male-dominated public spheres (Puwar & Raghuram, 2020; Rai, 2020). According to UNESCO (2012), in higher education women should be involved in teaching and management globally as men are (M. Rehman & Siddiqui, 2020). Women academicians in higher education could not achieve equality with men (Selthun, 2020). Hence, male and female in higher education is disproportionately 20 to 1 at senior career level (Sankar & Aruna, 2020). This means universities, like other spheres of public life, are not equally accessible to men and women (Selthun, 2020). Women academicians when working with male heads and colleagues face discriminatory attitudes towards the workplace (Semela et al., 2020). These experiences are not generally discussed and studied due to men dominated society (Stahl et al., 2020). Men are also responsible for the gendered pattern of interaction (Tran & Nguyen, 2020). Men have challenged the autonomy of women not only in higher education but also in the development of institutional rules, regulations, and policies that primarily cater to the needs of men (Wadia, 2020). Similarly, power is concentrated in the hands of men, a truth not challenged in academia until second-wave feminism, scholars questioned the taken-for-granted phenomenon in academia (Wier & Price, 2020). Women academicians although highly educated and skilled but the masculine nature of higher education undermines their intellect and authority (Yusufzada et al., 2020). As a result, higher education perceived as men spaces atypically ascribes them to conform men (Zulfqar, Hussain, & Ahmed, 2019). Thus, scholars started examining experiences of women academician visa vis to men in higher education institutions i.e., income, rewards, promotion, and gendered patterns.

Methodology

This research article skims findings of several research studies on women academics lived experiences across the world. It does not include any meta-analysis because desk review is mainly carried out to outline the research findings from different research databases. However, we adopted a systematic approach and criteria for the selection of the study. Furthermore, we had clear and defined criteria for considering the studies for review. Therefore, we focused on the studies conducted on women's academics and their lived experiences as academics in higher education institutions. Most of these studies covered women's academic experiences partially or completely in one or another dimension of higher education. We sorted out all the databases containing the journals on gender and higher education i.e., Tylor and Francis, Eric education, Science direct, and Google scholar. We selected these databases as they were easily accessible. We reviewed research articles, using the cited database software till reaching the point of saturation. For this article, we reviewed more than 150 research articles and a few reports and theses.

Results and Discussion

The account of the women's experiences across the world is presented below.

Women Experiences in Higher Education in Developed Countries

In the United States of America (USA), female academicians are less than males in higher education. Women academics earn less than men at each of the professorial ranks and any type of higher education institutions (Kalleberg, 2011). In higher education, part-time and low-paid positions among women have also been detected in countries such as the UK, Canada, Australia, and New Zealand (Hegarty, 2014). Researches show that number of women academicians is not fairly proportioned to men (J. Acker, 1990). The structure of higher education is mainly male-dominated since its inception (J. Acker, 2006). Women academicians, although entered in higher education but face the masculine nature of the institution. Similarly, In United Kingdom (UK), higher education is men dominated spaces, and female academicians do not progress as male academicians, explicit male preeminence in higher education (S. Acker & Armenti, 2004; Dyhouse, 2016). In the West, like other areas of the public domain, higher education institutions are men's spaces (Barton, 1998). Women academicians although occupying the power positions are less likely privileged than men in higher education institutions. Similarly, in Germany women experience the same marginality in higher education as in other parts of the world (Bayfield, Colebrooke, Pitt, Pugh, & Stutter, 2020). Likewise, women in France and Italy are also subjected to the masculine nature of higher education. Moreover, the phenomenon has been found same in France and Spain where men are occupying the spaces in higher education and women are kept at subverted positions (Caradonna, 2012). In Italy, higher education is mainly the men-dominated spheres, and women are found less likely to occupy the power positions (D'Amico, Vermigli, & Canetto, 2011). Like the USA, female academicians in Canada are less while men progress than women in higher education (Ledwith & Manfredi, 2000; Ren & Caudle, 2020; White, 2004). Japan In Norway, female academicians face the problem of adjusting the family and academic expectations and a similar problem has been found in Sweden, Singapore, Belgium, and Switzerland (Forster, 2001; Hegarty, 2014; Kalleberg, 2011).

Women Experiences in Higher Education in Developing Countries

Women experience a vivid gender gap in higher education in China where men are mainly formulating and implementing education policies (Ren & Caudle, 2020). Resultantly, women academicians are less likely found

in power positions and experience marginality (M. Rehman & Siddiqui, 2020). Similarly, men continue to underrepresent women in India's higher education where fewer women than men are exercising the power positions (Pathan, 2020). Women in India are mainly the mid-careers struggling to pursue faculty status and positions vis-a-vis men (Kumar & Singh, 2020). Women are found less likely in academic roles and responsibilities as compared to men (Jejeebhoy & Sathar, 2001). Likewise, men have mainly occupied the spaces in higher education in Bangladesh and Pakistan (Kumar & Singh, 2020). Men have developed the policies at the higher education level. Men are preferred in decision making and formulation and designing of policies at the national level (Unit, 2013). Women are limited to leadership positions. Disparities exist in Russian higher education where women have not achieved autonomy in academics as in other fields i.e., computer education and economic spheres. Although women achieved a better foothold in management and administrative position but still lag behind the academic positions (Unit, 2014). Women still have to explore the horizons in academia to take the roles and responsibilities as men have. In Georgia, the emphasis has been on the present situation of the workplace of women academicians in higher education (Khan, Khan, & Khan-Guide, 2020). The research focused on various institutional practices of subjugating women in promotion, salaries, and roles in universities (Singh-Sengupta, 2001). Malaysian society is patriarchal, area of experience for women academicians is based on family-work conflict as women in Indonesia face discrimination by men (Susanti, 2011). Increased workload pressures of family disrupt the academic demands of Indonesian academics (Unin, 2014). Despite a large number of women in higher education, it does not reflect that woman assuming power positions. For Malay women, due to traditional cultural values and norms of society Malay societal norms always favored men in academia and Malay women are facing organizational barriers perpetrated by men (H. M. Ali & Musah, 2012; Ong, 1990; Unin, 2010).

Women Experiences in Higher Education in African Countries

In Africa, higher education is male-dominated spaces. Women academicians are not fairly presented in higher education in most African countries (Hayward, 2020). Mama (2003) asserts that women in Africa are never deprived to seek careers in higher education but factually universities across Africa remained men's spaces culturally. The norms and values restricted women's growth as fast as men (Johnstone, 2004). Women academicians face many challenges due to atypical African culture to smoothen their career in higher education (Molla & Cuthbert, 2016). In the past, higher education was considered a reserved terrain for men which prevented women from pursuing a career in academia (Moodie, 2010). Women attempted time and again, built resilience and self-efficacy to attain successes in higher education (Riordan & Louw-Potgieter, 2011). Like other African countries, South Africa has a male-dominated atypical culture (Rudhumbu, 2016). In South African higher education women are fewer than men perusing careers (Sall, 2000). For the last few decades, measures have been taken to ensure the plan of action to mainstream the women in higher education but still, academia gave a rare space to women to reflect on their careers (Kamau, 2004). Similarly, in Ethiopia, higher education institutions are male-dominated with hierarchical order and hostile to women (Morley, 2010). The taken-for-granted assumptions of institutions operate to make women subverted (Molla & Cuthbert, 2016).

In Kenya, women's academic career experiences are either shaped by the indigenous cultural expectations prevailing in institutions or western gender subordination (Kamau, 2011). It is revealed that the career of women in higher education lags behind men due to the infeasible environment, but women are resisting to shape their careers (Kamau, 2004). Women aspirants of higher education resist, negotiate and subvert their positions to keep alive their identities in Kenya. In Nigeria, Odejide, Akanji, and Odekunle (2006) assert that women persistently face discrimination in higher education which hinders their abilities to seek higher positions. Adadevoh (2001) suggests that women need to be better equal to men in academia. Women experience a similar situation as in Kenya. In Ghana, researches on the experiences of women academicians have been limited (Morley, 2010). Only a few studies have been conducted that are insufficient and partially covering the women's experiences. Molla and Cuthbert (2016) noted imbalances in the higher education of Ghana. Women are not given proper space as men have in academia to progress. Tanzania Comparably to Kenya and Nigeria, the women's landscape is problematic (Britwum, Oduro, & Prah, 2014). Women academicians are not in a position to exercise their rights to seek change due to the masculine characteristics of institutions. Drawing on the women experiences of Cameroon, Egypt, Malawi, Mauritania, Nigeria, Senegal, Tanzania, and Uganda, it is therefore concluded that women in higher education unpacked uneven power relations and resources distribution among men and women in Africa (Moodie, 2010; Riordan & Louw-Potgieter, 2011; Rudhumbu, 2016; Sall, 2000).

Women Experiences in Higher Education in South Asia

Higher Education in Afghanistan is emerging where women enrollment in higher education is only 3 percent lowest in the world (Unit, 2013). The lowest intake level results in a low ratio of women entering higher education. Besides this, various cultural factors hindered women to progress in academia (Kakker & Bhandhari, 2015). Owing to this, men have doubled in academia than women. Gender Studies Institute, Kabir (2013) found that women academicians felt treated as 'second class citizens of the university'. He further asserts that women academicians are less likely involved in activities and hardly given any role as men do have. Consequently, women have fewer opportunities than men at universities. Compared to men, women staff have less access and

opportunities at the universities. According to the Unit (2013) of Bangladesh, universities are mainly men-dominated spaces where men are enjoying senior-level positions. There are fewer studies on women academicians in higher education. Verma, Seth, Subramanian, and Verma (2013) suggested that women academicians are underrepresented in higher education while the procedure of quality assurance, recruitment processes, and political influences mainly disrupt women's development. Jayaweera (1997a) noted that studies are conducted on gender, but problems of women academicians are never focused on by the researchers Kabir (2010) found that women academicians are not given the roles they deserve as academicians in universities. Major challenges for India include how to staff its rapidly expanding higher education (Khan et al., 2020). Rapidly expanding higher education of India has less ratio of female academicians. In most universities, women staffing issues are the main hindrance in academia (Jha, Minni, & Ahmed, 2020). Like other South Asian Countries, women academicians are not entrusted with power, prestige, and status as men have at senior academic positions (Jayaweera, 1997b). Chanana (2000) suggests that the cultural/structural issues are the hindrances in the development of women academicians where women academicians are deprived of roles and responsibilities. Rab (2010) concentrated the women's issues in higher education besides the patriarchal structure of society. Shah (2001) identified the main concerns of women academicians, roles and responsibilities ascribed to men, gender pay gaps, and exercise of power and status disadvantageous to women. Furthermore, Batool and Sajid (2013) show that structural factors such as mentoring, networking, selection and promotion practices, and gender equity are barriers to the women academicians in higher education. Ghaus and Raja (2013) elucidate women encounter familial and organizational barriers. Similarly, women are underrepresented in academia facing the multiple issues discussed above are also found similar in Nepal, Sri-Lanka, and Maldives (Morley, 2006).

Women Experiences in Higher Education in Pakistan

Pakistan, like other parts of the subcontinent, is very patriarchal (Afzal, Butt, Akbar, & Roshi, 2013). Men are leaders in the public and private domains (A. Ahmed & Hyder, 2008). In higher education institutions, women academicians are undermined in their capabilities in carrying out their daily routine tasks of class responsibilities (Z. Ahmed, 2009). Rules for the private and public domains, including universities, are designed, approved, and implemented by men (A. Ali, Tariq, & Topping, 2013). Women's visibility in the public domain is not equal to men's (Batool & Sajid, 2013). The literacy rate for males is greater than for females. The total number of women employed in the public domain is lesser than men (Batool, Sajid, & Shaheen, 2013). Women's employment in the public domain is dominantly in primary and secondary schools (Durrani, 2000). Women academicians are mostly assigned passive roles in internal and external issues of the department (Ghaus & Raja, 2013). The social structure of society has a significant impact upon the autonomy of women academicians serving in higher education institutions (Jabbar & Imran, 2013). Most women employed in higher educational institutions face different brick walls created by men that exclude them from active participation (Majid, 2020). Several studies from Pakistan are evident that women's experiences in higher education are shaped and directed by the social fabric of the society (H. Rehman et al., 2020; Shah, 2001).

Conclusion

The review vividly revealed that the situation is worst in developing countries. In the developing world, women academicians face more discrimination as compared to women academics in the developed world. The results revealed that society is male dominant structure and hostile to women. Furthermore, taken-for-granted gender assumptions and beliefs in higher education institutions operate to make women conform to structures of disadvantage and experience repressive gender relations. We reach on the argument that men academicians explicitly manipulate the fate of the women academicians in higher education. To raise women academics' voice at the global level, this study asserted that the current trend of women academicians in higher education needs to be examined in the different socio-cultural context. It is suggested that women can get senior and powerful positions if they are given a women-friendly environment and equitable chance in higher education.

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